

Addressing Occlusions in Upper Limb Kinematic Reconstruction

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Abstract—In this paper, we propose a new approach for human motion reconstruction based on Gaussian Mixture Probability Hypothesis Density (GM-PHD) Filter applied to human joint positions extracted from RGB-D camera. The results demonstrate that our approach outperforms the standard Kinect solution in occlusion scenarios and can be applied in robotics field. To evaluate the applicability of the approach, we employ it as interface to remotely control a drone.

Index Terms—Kinect One, GM-PHD, Occlusions and Drone

Marker-based optoelectronic systems are the gold standard for reconstructing kinematic characteristics of the human beings but have limitations such as long setup times, high costs and structured environments. This has led to the development of markerless approaches using RGB-D cameras like the Kinect One. However, these systems have lower accuracy and precision compared to optoelectronic systems and are prone to occlusions and joint misidentifications, which hinder image segmentation. To address occlusions, some methods fuse Kinect data with IMUs [1] or multiple Kinect sensors [2] using a Kalman Filter (KF), but these solutions can restrict natural movement or require a structured environment. In this paper, the joint occlusion is addressed by treating the Kinect kinematic reconstruction as a multitarget tracking problem. A Gaussian Mixture Probability Hypothesis Density (GM-PHD) filter is employed, because it does not require individual observations to be connected with any trace. Its performance is compared to an optoelectronic system, showing improvements over Kinect default algorithm, especially in handling occlusion. To validate the approach, its adoption in remote control of a drone is considered.

Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) are becoming more common in everyday life. To facilitate the communication between the user and drone, a gesture-based control strategy is introduced and tested. Its usability is compared with state-of-the-art gesture recognition methods, i.e. (Electromyography) EMG and keyboard control.

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I. METHODOLOGY

A. Gaussian Mixture PHD Filter

Traditional KF assumes a fixed number of objects with known identities, which may not perform well in complex scenarios such as occlusions. In contrast, Random Finite Sets (RFS) methods, such as the GM-PHD filter, offer a probabilistic description of the targets' states. The filter describes the uncertainty associated with the target states as a Gaussian mixture model. Each component represents a potential target with weights indicating the probability of the corresponding target's existence. Hence, in this case, the measurements (\mathbf{z}) and states (\mathbf{x}) are represented as RFS to improve accuracy. Density functions in target space (body joints) are used to represent the states, and the GM-PHD depicts the first moment of distribution on the RFS [3].

B. Filter Application

The GM-PHD filter processes the positions of nine joints detected by Kinect One in the image plane. In the prediction phase, a constant acceleration model is assumed. Each joint's state includes its position, velocity, and acceleration in the image plane. After obtaining the filtered data, the Pinhole equations are applied to determine the new 3D positions (x, y, z) in the Kinect frame, based on the z -axis coordinate. Moreover, we found out that, during the movement, joint distances vary with and without occlusions. Thus, a kinematic constraint between joints is applied to respect anatomical limits. The new position of a joint is calculated using the filtered positions of the proximal and distal joints [4].

II. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP & PROTOCOL

The experimental setup used to conduct the experiments includes the Kinect One camera, the Ryze Dji Tello drone, the Vicon motion capture system and the Myo Armband to ensure EMG drone control.

In accordance with ethical guidelines, this study has been determined to be exempt from obtaining approval from a

TABLE I
MEAN AND STANDARD DEVIATIONS FOR EACH SUBJECT.
S.-E. STANDS FOR "SHOULDER-ELBOW" AND E.-H FOR "ELBOW-HAND"

	#Subj.	Hand Occlusion		Elbow-Hand Occlusion	
		S.-E. std[mm]	E.-H. std[mm]	S.-E. std[mm]	E.-H. std[mm]
Kinect	1	20.5	16.4	35.4	37.9
Filter		8.3	9.6	15.0	17.0
Kinect	2	12.6	19.5	32.0	38.5
Filter		7.5	7.3	23.00	8.9
Kinect	3	24.1	23.6	29.7	49.9
Filter		13.8	9.4	20.7	12.7
Kinect	4	23.7	39.1	38.0	46.7
Filter		15.5	8.1	19.2	11.7

relevant review board since the research poses minimal risk. The experimental protocol consists of three test:

1) *First test*: The study aimed to compare joint position and angle data from Kinect One and the GM-PHD filter with the Vicon Vero 2.2 system. Four healthy (26 ± 2 aged), participants performed right shoulder abductions under varying occlusions: only hand and elbow-hand.

2) *Second test (Reaching task)*: One participant controlled the drone using gestures proposed in [4], repeating the task three times. The success rate was used as indicator.

3) *Third test*: The study validated the usability of the proposed approach as drone control modality by involving eight non-expert users (25 ± 4 aged) using three interfacing systems: Kinect, EMG and keyboard.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1) *First experimental test*: As demonstrated in Table I, during hand occlusion tasks, the kinematic constraint reduced the standard deviations of shoulder-elbow and elbow-hand lengths, with a 44.4% and 59.1%, respectively. Whereas, in the case of elbow-hand occlusions, reductions of 41.5% and 69.7% were observed. As regards the position of the hand, the filter resulted in a 43.7% reduction in the mean error and a 52.3% in the standard deviation, while in the elbow flexion the performance was comparable to the ones obtained with the Kinect (Table II). In the case of increased occlusion (Table III), the mean error and standard deviation for hand position exhibited a 55.8% and 57.4% reduction, respectively. The reduction in elbow flexion angle in mean and standard deviation were 36.3% and 70.2%, respectively. Wilcoxon tests confirmed significant differences in limb length deviations, hand position error and elbow flexion angle (only under occlusion), showing that the filter outperforms the Kinect.

TABLE II
HAND OCCLUSION, MEAN ERRORS.

#Subj.	Kinect Elbow Flex. Error[°]	Filter Elbow Flex. Error[°]	Kinect Hand Pos. Error[mm]	Filter Hand Pos. Error[mm]
1	6.1 ± 7.7	5.9 ± 7.2	50.7 ± 29.4	27.7 ± 18.3
2	2.3 ± 4.3	3.5 ± 5.4	14.8 ± 24.9	11.8 ± 11.6
3	1.7 ± 9.7	3.1 ± 6.7	23.3 ± 41.9	6.9 ± 17.0
4	6.7 ± 19.3	1.4 ± 4.1	32.2 ± 57.1	21.2 ± 23.8

TABLE III
ELBOW - HAND OCCLUSION, MEAN ELBOW FLEXION AND HAND POSITION ERROR

#Subj.	Kinect Elbow Flex. Error[°]	Filter Elbow Flex. Error[°]	Kinect Hand Pos. Error[mm]	Filter Hand Pos. Error[mm]
1	8.7 ± 16.2	7.4 ± 8.8	57.3 ± 57.6	33.5 ± 35.8
2	10.1 ± 44.3	9.6 ± 11.5	60.5 ± 82.9	25.3 ± 25.7
3	9.6 ± 42.8	3.5 ± 6.8	50.1 ± 88.8	16.1 ± 26.0
4	22.3 ± 63.5	8.5 ± 14.6	64.2 ± 84.1	28.4 ± 40.4

2) *Second experimental test*: Even though the occlusion induced by the obstacle is present (Fig.1), a success rate of 100% was achieved.¹

Fig. 1. First trial result. In blue Kinect and in red the filtered data.

3) *Third experimental test*: Fig.2 shows that the Kinect has the highest usability score (75), compared to the keyboard (73) and EMGs (71) interfacing systems, indicating its strength as drone control interfacing system.

Fig. 2. System usability scale (SUS) boxplots, keyboard and EMG gestures.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The proposed human motion reconstruction method can robustify the Kinect One detections especially in presence of occlusions. The comparative analysis with other gesture-based technologies for remotely controlling a drone demonstrated the higher performance of the proposed approach.

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¹The multimedia material: <https://youtu.be/tx6evFBOHKE>